

INTERRELATION OF ELECTRONIC, AUTOMATIC AND AUTOMATED VOCABULARY CONCEPTS

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Abstract. This thesis is devoted to the relationship of electronic, automatic and automated vocabulary concepts. The main advantages of electronic versions of dictionaries are also noted. Moreover, the analysis of electronic and traditional features of dictionaries have been identified in the article.

Keywords: Lexicography, Electronic Dictionary, multimedia tools, electronic publication, glossary.

The development of modern information technologies increases the possibilities of remote organization, management, and control of the educational process. As a result, distance education began to take the leading status of computer education 1. Electronic educational publications - various lectures, seminars, laboratory work and case technologies corresponding to the curriculum. 2. Multimedia educational programs - training courses with animation and sound tracking. 3. Electronic textbooks - an electronic educational publication designed to automate teaching. 4. Electronic training manuals - separate sections of the subject, a set of exercises or problems, a reference book, etc.

According to D. Sayfurov, electronic educational literature allows to eliminate the shortcomings of traditional teaching methods. In recent years, the creation of electronic educational literature and the development of electronic dictionary-informative materials have developed sharply. It is possible to distribute electronic educational publications via the network. Another important aspect of electronic educational literature is that the educational material and visual materials in it do not wear out and do not wear out, do not require a lot of space and volume for storage. The creation of electronic educational literature is increasing significantly more than printed publications. [1]

The word "lexicography" comes from the Greek words lexikos "relating to a word, vocabulary" and grapho "I write". Therefore, lexicography means: "I write words" or "I write dictionaries."

M. V. Avdeeva states that in the modern sense, "lexicography is the theory and practice of compiling linguistic, linguistic dictionaries, as opposed to non-linguistic, encyclopedic dictionaries. Lexicography as a scientific discipline is complex, but the defining feature of lexicography is its practical orientation. Scientists say that theoretical lexicography studies the development of the macro-structure and micro-structure of the dictionary, the development of the typology of dictionaries, and the history of the development of lexicography.

According to M.V. Avdeyeva, the macrostructure of the dictionary determines the selection of the dictionary, the size and character of the dictionary, the principles of material placement. Practical lexicography can be described as the process of compiling various types of dictionaries based on theoretical developments" [2].

According to most experts, as society becomes more informed, the nature of modern lexicography is also changing.

Currently, the use of computers for lexicographic work is becoming more and more widespread both in scientific research and in the practical construction of dictionaries. Changing research tools lead to the emergence of new vocabulary technologies. Today, the volume of lexicographic works performed with the help of computers is so large that many experts express many opinions about the emergence of a relevant branch of the science of computer lexicography.

Computer lexicography refers to:

- 1) a rapidly developing branch of the computer industry;
- 2) methods, technology and individual methods of using computer technologies in the theory and practice of creating dictionaries, an applied scientific science studied in linguistics.

E.Yu. Vaulina defines computer lexicography as "a set of dictionaries available in electronic form, regardless of the method of creation." According to the researcher, the electronic version of the dictionary, in particular, "quick retrieval of information that is available somewhere in the dictionary and that directly responds to the query formulated by the user is a convenient development designed to provide an opportunity" [3].

For example, lugat.uz, gramota.ru, imlo.uz, vseslova.ru, km.ru and some other sites provide an opportunity to search for information related to a given word in a whole group of dictionaries at the same time. V. P. Selegey has a different point of view, according to which "computer lexicography is a special direction of practical lexicography that has its own approaches not only to display, but also to the content of the dictionary." In his opinion, "the electronic dictionary is a special lexicographic

object that can implement and put into circulation many effective ideas that are not required for various reasons in paper dictionaries" [4].

A. V. Shlyakhova gives different descriptions in her work called "Electronic Dictionary". In our opinion, the following features are the main ones:

- reversibility (arbitrarily, at the request of the user, change the input and output languages);

- flexibility (a set of technical methods for simplifying the search form in the easy use of the dictionary; convenience for getting the necessary information in a short time);

- dynamism (filling, correcting, removing outdated data).

- plurality (multilingualism);

- volume (the ability to include any number of vocabulary units).

Additional functions include the use of multimedia tools to provide different types of information (audio, video, radio information, animation, games, forums, notes according to the different requirements and interests of each category of users). [5].

Summarizing the above, it can be noted that one of the main advantages of electronic types of dictionaries is the following: they allow users to add new words to the dictionary available to users, while reprinting in the printed edition It is not possible to add additional information without But there is another reason for the need to create electronic dictionaries: to automate the search for information needed by the user. This is especially true in the modern world, where the speed of finding information, the speed of life and the need to quickly get the results of any search are of fundamental importance.

However, electronic dictionaries are not widely used for several reasons. To find out these reasons, we conduct a functional comparison of electronic dictionaries and traditional dictionaries and identify the advantages and disadvantages of both types of dictionaries.

Most electronic dictionaries perform five functions:

- 1) parallel request during operation;
- 2) change and correction (copy - paste);
- 3) notes and notes;
- 4) export;
- 5) printing.

The electronic form offers great opportunities. These possibilities are much wider than in print and they depend on two factors:

1) electronic publication can contain not only texts and pictures, but also animation, video and sound;

2) the electronic publication has interactivity, that is, it provides the passage through hyperlinks and even personal participation in the simulation of virtual space.

After analyzing the characteristics of electronic and traditional publications, we have identified the following differences in their forms:

1) a computer is required to work with an electronic form and the RAM of the device, to work with a paper form - a book and the skill of using it;

2) the creation of a traditional type of dictionary requires printing supplies and printing services, and for an electronic dictionary, programming skills, a computer that reads data, etc., are required to be combined into a single product; thus, we can talk about the ecological safety of the production of electronic dictionaries;

3) an electronic dictionary can contain the most complete information and references, a traditional dictionary can have a limited volume, so the amount of information entered when creating it should be limited;

4) work with paper dictionaries takes place in a linear way ("search for a word by nomenclature or throughout the text" [3]), and with electronic dictionaries you can work in a fragmented way ("search for a word only by name ("nomenclature") [3]);

5) electronic dictionaries provide more opportunities for publication design than traditional dictionaries: use of colors, pagination, visualization of various types of information; on the other hand, most paper dictionaries lack color design, features are minimal, and information presentation is rigid;

6) electronic dictionaries allow the user to search easily and quickly; the information in them is structured in such a way that the user can perform various searches (informative - the user is interested in the answer to the question, but it is not so important where it is located, navigation helps with this.)

7) the electronic dictionary can be equipped with a constantly working information update system, traditional dictionaries do not have such capabilities;

8) the electronic dictionary may contain notes, comments, etc., besides, it may be provided with cross-references to other dictionaries or references;

9) electronic dictionaries take up less space (on the desk and in the library) and are easier to use than paper dictionaries;

10) the electronic dictionary does not age, its pages are not damaged, torn and folded.

It follows from the above that the two types of dictionaries differ in the basis of information presentation, which determines the advantages and disadvantages of both. Despite some shortcomings inherent in electronic dictionaries, especially in technical terms (instability in the operation of hard drives, software malfunctions, including personal computer crashes), they are of great value to the user. has advantages.

Creation of electronic dictionaries is a promising, actively developing field of modern lexicography. At the same time, there are no specific rules or methods for creating such dictionaries, a single standard, general criteria that determine the quality of this type of dictionaries.

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